

KNOWLEDGE INTEGRATION ACTIONS. INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP WORKSHOP WITH WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN CLIZA, COCHABAMBA

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Summary

Knowledge integration actions propose a paradigm shift in development cooperation, where communities become protagonists of their own improvement based on their local knowledge. Under this premise, the NGO Ciudadanía and the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya carried out an innovation and entrepreneurship workshop in Cliza, Cochabamba, with a group of women entrepreneurs from the Valle Alto region, whose businesses cover sectors such as livestock, bakery and confectionery, fabrics, and gastronomy.

During the two days of the workshop, we worked with a participatory methodology, based on group work and the use of guided tools, to strengthen the management and innovation capacities of the participants. The sequence of activities took them from an analysis of their current production processes, the identification of their challenges and the definition of their aspirations, to the selection of a key improvement and the development of an action plan to implement it. Likewise, the use of digital tools as a resource for research and commercialization was explored.

As a main result, each participant ended the action with a concrete, realistic and short-term oriented improvement plan for their venture, with specific actions in areas such as product innovation, cost optimization, and commercial and distribution methods and strategies. The workshop not only generated practical solutions to problems identified by them, but also provided them with a replicable method of analysis and planning, thus strengthening their autonomy and the sustainability of their economic activities. The experience shows the potential of this approach to promote local development from the bottom up

1. Introduction

Knowledge integration actions

The action described in this document is part of a broader initiative based on what have been called knowledge integration actions. This approach is born from the conviction that, in order to achieve sustainable results, the incorporation of technological and management improvements in vulnerable communities must be a process led by them. Too often, externally designed solutions fail to take root, as they do not align with local realities, knowledge, and aspirations.

Knowledge integration actions therefore propose a paradigm shift. In this, instead of being recipients of solutions, communities become protagonists of their own development. It is based on the premise that the most powerful and lasting innovation is the one that arises from the very heart of the community, combining valuable local knowledge with external tools and methodologies. In this model, external technicians and facilitators do not impose a direction, but act as catalysts, bringing new perspectives and helping to structure the process of discovery and creation led by the participants themselves.

This model of innovation from within is based on several pillars:

- Recognize and value local knowledge. Communities have a deep understanding of their environment, their challenges and their capacities. This knowledge is the most important asset for building relevant and sustainable solutions.
- Promote autonomy. It seeks to strengthen the capacity of communities to manage their own projects, adapting and improving them continuously in the future.
- Promote social innovation. It stimulates the creation of solutions that respond to the social and economic challenges of communities, promoting equity, inclusion and sustainability.

This work philosophy has already been applied and validated in previous experiences. A direct antecedent of this action is the workshop carried out with artisans from the Wayúu Majali community, whose results and methodology are included in the report "Actions for the integration of knowledge. Workshop with the artisans of the Wayúu Majalí community in La Guajira". This action in Bolivia, together with two others focused on the field of rural energy and developed in La Guajira (Colombia) and Cochabamba (Bolivia), is part of a series of interventions that seek to consolidate and adapt this model of cooperation, demonstrating its flexibility and effectiveness in various cultural and productive contexts.

Context of the action

The workshop reported here was aimed at a group of women entrepreneurs from various municipalities that make up the Upper Valley region of Cochabamba, mainly from Cliza, Punata, Arbieta and Tolata, among others. This region, located southeast of the city of Cochabamba, is historically known as the "breadbasket of Bolivia" for its fertile land and important agricultural production. The local economy is largely based on agriculture, with crops of corn, wheat, potatoes and a notable fruit production, highlighting the peaches of Arbieta. Likewise, livestock activity,

commerce and traditional gastronomy, such as the elaboration of chicha and rosquetes in Punata, are fundamental pillars of life in the valley.

Figure 1. Map with the city of Cliza and others where participants came

The socioeconomic context of the Upper Valley is marked by important structural challenges that directly affect the viability of local enterprises. The region has a poverty rate that exceeds 50%, a figure considerably higher than the Bolivian national average. This situation is characteristic of rural areas of the country, where limited access to public services such as health or education aggravates the vulnerability of families. Added to this is a high rate of labor informality, which in Bolivia reaches more than 70% of workers, with a special incidence in the agricultural sector, where many of the participants operate.

This situation of economic precariousness disproportionately affects women. In Bolivia, four out of ten women live in poverty, a figure that is exacerbated in rural and indigenous areas such as the Valle Alto. The labour force participation gap between men and women is approximately 26%, largely due to social norms that place the main burden of unpaid domestic and care work on women. These barriers, coupled with difficulties in accessing land ownership and markets, limit their economic autonomy and reinforce their dependence on small-scale, often informal, enterprises.

The action was carried out by a team from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya¹ in collaboration with the NGO Ciudadanía, Comunidad de Estudios Sociales y Acción Pública, which facilitated the convening and organization of the workshop. Ciudadanía is a non-governmental organization founded on July 9, 2004 in the city of Cochabamba, where it currently has its headquarters. Its mission is focused on the production of socially relevant knowledge and the promotion of dialogue and public action to improve the quality of life, especially that of historically excluded groups.

¹ The activities of the members of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya team were partially funded by the university's own Centre for Development Cooperation, as part of the project "Entrepreneurship action and inclusive innovations for vulnerable communities" (project 2025-A004).

The intervention took place in the municipality of Cliza, in the department of Cochabamba, Bolivia, on July 17 and 18, 2024, under the title "Sowing Improvements, Harvesting the Future". The sessions took place in facilities provided by the Autonomous Municipal Government of Cliza².

Figure 2. Photograph of the whole group

2. Content, methodology and participants

Content

The design of the content and the programming of the activities are directly based on the approach of integration of knowledge and co-creation. The sequence of activities is a guided itinerary designed for the participants themselves to build, step by step, their improvement plans based on their own reality. It begins with the "business map" to start from local knowledge and the experience of the entrepreneurs. From there, the methodology accompanies them in a process that goes from the diagnosis of their current situation and the definition of their aspirations, to the selection of a strategic focus and the development of a concrete action plan. The Table 1 describes each of the activities designed for this purpose, while the Table 2 presents the schedule in which they were organized. The original plan was adapted to the dynamics of the group and, for greater clarity in this report, the six activities finally carried out are presented sequentially.

² We thank the Autonomous Municipal Government of Cliza for its support of this activity.

Table 1. Proposed activities

Activity	Description
1. My Business Map Today	Define in a table the key steps of the production process of each participant, from the beginning to the end. For each step, detail the resources used, the people involved, and an estimate of the cost and time required.
2. Identifying My Challenges	Identify, for each step of the previously prepared business map, the specific challenges or difficulties encountered by the entrepreneurs, writing them down on a worksheet that connects the problem with the phase of the process where it occurs.
3. My dream, my business in the future	Imagine and describe the vision of the business one year ahead. Use a chart to write down the main ideas of the dream, organized by topics such as products, customers, suppliers, finances, and personal well-being.
4. Generative social media and software	Practically explore the use of digital tools, including social networks (such as Pinterest and Instagram) for inspiration and product promotion, and artificial intelligence software (ChatGPT) as a source of information and ideas for the business.
5. Choosing My Key Improvement	Connect the identified challenges with the defined aspirations. From this connection, generate several opportunities for improvement and, finally, select a single key improvement on which to focus the action plan.
6. My improvement plan	Develop a detailed action plan on a worksheet. Starting from the chosen key improvement, define the specific steps to follow, the resources needed for each step, the person responsible for executing it, and the expected start and end dates.

Table 2. Activities and schedules of the action

Day	Timetable	Activity
Day 1	9:00 - 9:30	Welcome and Our Journey Together
	9:30 - 10:30	Activity 1. My Business Map Today
	10:30 - 11:15	Activity 2. Identifying My Challenges
	11:15 - 11:45	Coffee Break
	11:45 - 13:00	Activity 2. Identifying My Challenges (continued)
	13:00 - 14:00	Lunch
	14:00 - 16:00	Activity 3. My Dream: My Business in the Future
	16:00 - 16:15	Closing of Day 1
Day 2	9:00 - 9:30	Welcome and Review
	9:30 - 10:30	Activity 4. Generative social media and Software
	10:30 - 11:15	Coffee Break
	11:15 - 11:45	Activity 5. Choosing My Key Improvement
	11:45 - 13:00	Lunch
	13:00 - 14:00	Activity 6. My Improvement Plan
	14:00 - 16:00	Presentation of diplomas and farewell.

Characteristics and interests of the participants

The group of participants in the activities was diverse and representative of the productive reality of the Upper Valley. Their ventures include activities such as livestock, Bakery and confectionery, the preparation of juices and breakfasts, the sale of vegetables, and weaving. All of them are women who are actively looking for opportunities to improve their income and the quality of life of their families. Many had previous experience in training and had received incentives or seed capital from local institutions, demonstrating their commitment and proactivity.

In terms of their educational level, the group was heterogeneous, with women who had basic training and others who had completed primary, secondary and even higher technical education. Although their mother tongue is Quechua, most of the participants were fluent in Spanish, which allowed this to be the vehicular language of the sessions. The vast majority of the attendees had a mobile phone and used it with ease, a relevant factor for the subsequent introduction of digital tools.

The attendance at the conference was remarkable. On the first day, 30 women participated, and on the second day, 25. Of the total of 36 women registered, 19 of them attended both full days.

Methodology

As a fundamental element of the methodology, and to ensure active participation, work in small groups was encouraged. The plenary sessions were held in Spanish. However, since the mother tongue of most of the participants is Quechua, the members of the Citizenship team facilitated understanding by making clarifications and comments in this language whenever necessary, thus ensuring that language barriers were not an obstacle.

The structure of the different activities followed the same dynamic pattern in three phases. First, the topic to be discussed and the tool or template that would be used to guide the reflection were presented. This was followed by a space for discussion in the working groups, where participants shared their experiences and applied the tool to their own businesses. Finally, each group presented its results to the plenary, generating a sharing that allowed general conclusions to be drawn and enrich collective learning.

The Figure 3 shows the working groups developing one of the activities.

Figure 3. Working group carrying out one of the activities

To facilitate interaction, the participants were organized into six working groups, by entrepreneurs from the same productive sector - weaving group (artisans), breakfast group, livestock group, bakery and confectionery group, and, due to the number of participants in this activity, two juice groups.

A flexible methodological approach was adopted that combined group and individual work according to the nature of each activity. The first phases of the workshop, focused on the diagnosis (the business map, challenges and dreams), were mainly carried out in groups. This approach allowed the problems and aspirations common to each sector to emerge. On the contrary, the definition of specific objectives and the preparation of improvement plans were mostly addressed individually. This duality responds to a practical logic: while challenges and opportunities are often shared within the same sector, concrete action plans depend to a large extent on the resources, capacities and personal factors of each entrepreneur.

3. Development of activities

3.1 Analysis by activities

Activity 1. My Business Map Today

During the first activity, working in groups, the participants proceeded to draw up the map of their businesses. The objective was to obtain a structured vision of their production processes through the use of a table that broke down each undertaking into a sequence of steps. For each step, from initial planning or purchase to final sale, the groups detailed the resources needed, the people involved, and an estimate of cost and time. In the Figure 4 The result of the work of one of the groups is shown.

Figure 4. Example worksheet of "Activity 1. The map of my business today"³

Actividad 1. Hoja de trabajo: El Mapa de Mi Negocio HOY

Nombre de la Emprendedora: _____

Mi Actividad Principal (Emprendimiento): Venta de desayuno y repases

Paso	Qué recursos utilizo	Personas que participan	Costo y tiempo
Inicio:	Capital - Harina - Canela - Aceite - Azúcar - Agua	Familia hijos e hijas	Costo = 500
Paso 2:	Compra Insumos	hijos e hijas	Tiempo 2h
Paso 3:	Preparado de desayuno	hijos e hijas	2 horas
Paso 4:	Traslado del desayuno	- hijo - contrato móvil para trabajo	40 min.
Paso 5:	Venta del desayuno	- yo	6 horas
Paso 6:	Ofrecer el producto al cliente	yo	6 horas
Final:	Recopio de la venta y retorno a casa	yo	40 min.

In the resource's column, the responses included both the specific raw materials of each business and the cost of one of the purchases they make, ranging from 200 to 5,000 bolivianos, such as. For example, the gastronomy entrepreneurs listed ingredients such as potatoes, rice, chicken or vegetables, while those in bakery and confectionery mentioned flour and those in fabrics, wool and threads. Tools such as ovens, knitting machines and kitchen utensils were also identified.

The analysis of the people who participate revealed an important piece of information about the structure of these enterprises. Participants consistently noted the involvement of their closest family circle. Phrases such as "me and my family", "my daughters help me" or the mention of "my mother" appeared recurrently, which indicates that these businesses are based on a family support network that intervenes in different phases of the process. In addition to the family, other external actors such as suppliers and the customers themselves were identified.

³ Translation of the figure to English:

Step	What resources do I use?	People who participate	Cost and time
Start:	Capital - Flour, Cinnamon, Oil, Oats, Sugar	Family - sons and daughters	Cost = 500
Step 2:	Purchase of Supplies	sons and daughters	Time 2h
Step 3:	Preparation of the breakfast	sons and daughters	2 hours
Step 4:	Transport of the breakfast	- daughter - Hired transport for transfer	40 min.
Step 5:	Sale of the breakfast	- me	6 hours
Step 6:	Offering the product to the client	me	6 hours
Final:	Collection of the sale and return home	me	40 min.

In terms of cost and time, estimates provided by the groups suggest that precise data are not available, pointing to an informal approach to management. A significant observation of the worksheets is the clear distinction made between material inputs and labour. The cost of inputs was systematically quantified in monetary terms, while the participants' own work was quantified as an investment of time, measured in minutes, hours, or even days, but with no monetary value assigned. This exercise allowed the groups to visualize the flow of their activities in an orderly manner, which laid the groundwork for subsequent challenge analysis.

Activity 2. Identifying my challenges.

In the second activity, the participants used the business map they had previously developed as a guide to identify the challenges and difficulties they face in their ventures. On their worksheets, they were required to connect each challenge to the specific step in the process in which it occurred, which facilitated a deeper analysis of the issues. In the Figure 5 The result of the work of one of the groups is shown.

The work in the groups allowed a series of common challenges to emerge that can be grouped into several categories:

- Economic and cost challenges. This was the most frequently mentioned challenge. The participants almost unanimously pointed out "the rise in the price of products" or that "everything has gone up and there is not enough money". This problem directly affects their profitability, since, as one of them noted, "the buyer does not want to pay more". The difficulty in accessing inputs is compounded by transportation costs, which have also increased.
- Production and operational challenges. In this area, problems related to consistency and efficiency of work were identified. In bakery and confectionery, for example, they mentioned that "sometimes my dough does not come out well, it does not ferment well" or that "in baking it sometimes burns." The weavers pointed to the lack of "standardized measures" and the farmers to the impact of external factors such as "the frost that affects the growth of alfalfa."
- Commercial and market challenges. Competition was a recurring theme, described as "there's a lot of competition." The difficulty in selling was also mentioned, either because they cannot find customers or because they negotiate prices downwards. The lack of adequate transportation to get the products on sale was also pointed out as a major obstacle.
- Management challenges and skills. Some participants identified needs that go beyond production. One of them explicitly noted the "lack of recipes, novelties," and another recognized the need to improve their "commercial and negotiation skills." This suggests an awareness of the importance of innovation and management to grow their businesses.

Figure 5. Example of a worksheet for activity 2. Identifying my challenges.⁴

Actividad 2. Hoja de trabajo: Identificando Mis Retos

Nombre de la Emprendedora: _____

¿En qué Paso de mi Mapa encuentro un reto?	¿Cuál es el Reto o la Dificultad que encuentre?
1 Paso	Que todo los precios a subido
2 Paso	nos olvidamos o hacer rotar nuestro dinero
3 paso	- Habilidades Comerciales y Negociación - a veces me sale mal el desarrollo - Falta recetas, novedades de desayuno
4 paso 5 paso	- A veces no hay auto - (Negociar auto) - A veces no termino la venta (plan venta)
6 Final	A veces hay mucha competencia A veces me olvido algo de mis cosas

↳ Hacer listas e cheques
↳

⁴ Translation of the figure to English:

In what Step of my Map do I find a challenge?	What is the Challenge or Difficulty that I find?
Step 1	That all the Prices have gone up
Step 2	we have trouble rotating our money (or "managing our cash flow")
Step 3	- Commercial and Negotiation Skills - Sometimes the breakfast turns out badly for me - lack of recipes, new breakfast items
Step 4	- Sometimes there is no car (Negotiate car)
Step 5	- Sometimes I don't finish the Sale (Sales Plan)
Step 6 final	- Sometimes there is a lot of competition - Sometimes I forget some of my things
	Arrow pointing to: Make lists / Checking

The set of challenges identified demonstrates a high degree of awareness on the part of the participants about the limitations and pressures they face. The analysis paints a picture where women entrepreneurs face an economic environment of rising costs that puts pressure on their profit margins. At the same time, the identification of operational and management challenges indicates not only an opportunity for improvement, but also the ability of the participants themselves to recognize the need to standardize processes and develop new business skills that allow them to differentiate themselves in a competitive market.

Activity 3. My dream, my business in the future.

In the third activity, "My dream, my business in the future", participants were invited to project a long-term vision for their ventures. Using a worksheet, they were to describe what they would like their business to look like in a year, organizing their aspirations into different areas such as work and products, suppliers, customers, finances, and their personal well-being. An example of the result of this activity is shown in the Figure 6.

The participants' responses revealed a remarkable ambition and desire to transform their current activities into more established businesses. Your dreams can be grouped into several key areas:

- Growth and scalability. A common aspiration was to significantly expand the size and scope of its operations. The dreams included goals such as "expanding my breakfast business to opening a restaurant," "having a modern feedlot with about 30 heads," or, in the case of the weavers, "having my own shop or business stand."
- Access to new markets. The participants showed a clear interest in overcoming the limitations of local sales. They expressed the desire to "sell in shops in the city", to have customers with a "tourist" or even "foreign" profile. The most ambitious aspiration in this regard was to "export to other countries", indicating a business vision that transcends regional borders.
- Improvement of the value proposition. The entrepreneurs also focused on the quality and recognition of their products. They wanted their products to be "better known in the market", offer "more variety" and "improve quality". The importance of the relationship with customers was also mentioned, hoping that they "value my work and my seasoning."
- Financial stability. Increasing revenue was a central objective, expressed with goals such as "my money is tripled," "to have better profits," or "for my business to make a lot of money." This desire for economic growth was directly linked to the possibility of reinvesting to improve one's own business.
- Personal fulfilment and well-being. Beyond the economic, the dreams reflected a deep personal dimension. The participants expressed the desire to "enjoy my work more", "feel happy doing my things" and have "more time for myself and my family". The greatest pride, for many, would be "to be happy to have achieved my business" and that it served as an example and inspiration.

Figure 6. Sample worksheet for activity 3. My dream, my business in the future⁵.

Actividad 3. Hoja de trabajo: Mi Sueño Mi Negocio en el FUTURO

Nombre de la Emprendedora: _____

Vamos a usar esta tabla para anotar las ideas principales de nuestro sueño.

Tema de mi Sueño	¿Cómo me gustaría que fuera mi negocio en un año?
Mi Trabajo y Mis Productos	- Tener un puesto para la venta de tejidos. - Entrega de prendas por mayos. - Exportar a otros países
Mis proveedores	- Tiendas mayoristas que hacen entrega a precio rebajado y de buena calidad.
Mis Clientes	- Hombres, mujeres, jóvenes - extranjeros
Mi Dinero	- Tener mejores ganancias - Mejorar la producción
Mi Bienestar y mi Tiempo	- Contratar trabajadores o ayudantes - Trabajar en grupo
Mi Mayor Orgullo (Lo que me haría sentir más feliz)	- Contar con mi propia tienda o puesto de negocio. - Generar mi propio ingreso para ayudar a mi familia

⁵ Translation of the figure to English:

Theme of my Dream	How would I like my business to be in a year?
My Work and My Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To have a stall for the sale of weavings. Delivery of garments wholesale. Export to other countries.
My Suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shops, wholesalers who make deliveries at a reduced price and of good quality.
My Customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Men, women, young people. Foreigners
My Money	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To have better profits. Improve production
My Well-being and my Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hire workers or helpers. Work in a group
My Greatest Pride (What would make me feel happiest)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To have my own shop or business stall. Generate my own income to help my family.

Overall, this activity marked a turning point in the dynamics of the workshop. The aspirations of the participants demonstrated a shift in perspective from day-to-day problem management to a long-term strategic vision. Their dreams were not limited to incremental improvements, but aimed at a structural transformation of their enterprises, seeking to professionalize them, expand them and turn them into a source of pride and well-being both economically and personally.

Activity 4. Social networks and generative software.

A salient aspect of the project was the participants' keen interest in Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly ChatGPT. They were made easy to download and use this tool, which generated enormous enthusiasm for the possibility of consulting and obtaining information. The need to reinforce the importance of good context when asking questions to AI was noted in order to obtain accurate and useful answers. The potential of platforms such as TikTok, Pinterest and Instagram as tools for design research, product promotion and marketing to a wider audience was also explored.

Figure 7. Diagram on the workshop blackboard⁶.

⁶ Translation of the figure to English:

Left Column (Day 1 Summary)	Centre Column (Digital Tools & Sectors)	Right Column (Handicrafts Tools)
DAY 1: 1) MY BUSINESS MAP - STEPS - RESOURCES - COST/TIME 2) CHALLENGES 3) DREAMS - PRODUCTS - CUSTOMERS - MONEY - WELL-BEING AND TIME - MY GREATEST PRIDE	PINTEREST FOOD - DRINKS CAKE AND BAKERY/PASTRY www.gemini.google A.I. ChatGPT Gemini SOCIAL NETWORKS FACEBOOK INSTAGRAM WHATSAPP TIKTOK	HANDICRAFTS Search engine: GOOGLE PINTEREST

This interest was later materialized in the proposals and concrete action plans that they developed in the activity. In several of the worksheets, participants identified social media as a key tool for marketing. For example, some entrepreneurs included in their plan's actions such as "promote on WhatsApp", "publish and offer product on networks" or, more specifically, "open a Facebook page" to manage orders. Likewise, the need to have the basic resources for this was recognized, such as a "mobile phone with the program downloaded" or access to the "Internet", which demonstrates a clear intention to integrate these digital tools into their sales strategies.

It should be pointed out, at this point, that the use of social networks and generative software has the danger of generating an effect of imitating patterns of behaviour that are alien to the reality of those who use them and, without a doubt, not always positive for them. The discussion with the participants emphasized the idea that the possibilities that are contemplated must be contemplated with an analytical and critical spirit. In this sense, the idea of co-creation and integration of knowledge on which this action was based is especially appropriate, not only for this type of community, but probably for any type of group.

Activity 5. Choosing my key improvement.

In the fourth activity, the participants carried out a strategic focusing exercise. The aim was to connect the concrete problems identified in the challenge activity with the long-term aspirations defined in the dream activity. Using a worksheet, each entrepreneur linked one of her challenges to the part of her dream that it prevented her from achieving. From this connection, they generated several "opportunities for improvement" and, among them, they had to make a crucial decision: choose a single "key improvement" on which they would focus all their planning effort. In the Figure 8 The result of the work of one of the groups is shown.

Figure 8. Sample worksheet for activity 4. Choosing my key improvement⁷.

Actividad 4. Hoja de trabajo: Elijiendo Mi Mejora Clave

Nombre de la emprendedora: ayare v. 25 Ferrer

Hoja de Trabajo: De Mis Retos a Mis Mejoras

Usa esta tabla para anotar las ideas de tus sueños.

Mi Reto de HOY (El problema)	La parte de mi SUEÑO que se conecta con este reto	Mi Oportunidad de Mejora (La idea para solucionarlo)
el dinero	tener mi propia pasteleria	ir a ambular en los mercados
precios competencias	que la gente conozca mis productos	ofrecer a las tiendas llegas a mas gente
falta de ingredientes	Dar empleos	puedo promociar por whatsapp
por falta de clientes	la gente que conosca los sabores de mis productos	puedo vender mas ofreciendo a otras tiendas

Mi Decisión Final

Ya tienes varias ideas de mejora. Ahora tienes que elegir **SOLO UNA**. Esta es la mejora en la que vas a trabajar mañana para hacer un plan detallado.

De todas estas oportunidades, ¿cuál es la mejora que te parece más importante ahora? ¿Cuál es la que te daría más energía y ganas de empezar?

Anota aquí tu decisión. Esta será tu Mejora Clave. Mi Mejora Clave para trabajar mañana es:

ESTANDARIZAR RECETA!
BUSCAR RECETAS INNOVADORAS
HACER FORMAS Y PRESENTACIONES INNOVADORAS

⁷ Translation of the figure to English:

Worksheet: From My Challenges to My Improvements. Use this table to write down the improvement ideas that occur to you by connecting your challenges with your dreams.

My Challenge TODAY (The problem)	The part of my DREAM that connects with this challenge	My Improvement Opportunity (The idea to solve it)
Money	To have my own pastry shop	Go walk around the markets
Prices Competition	For people to know my products	Offer to shops Reach more people
Lack of ingredients	Provide jobs	I can promote on whatsapp
Due to lack of customers	For people to know the flavours of my products	I can sell more by offering to other shops

My Final Decision. You already have several improvement ideas. Now you have to choose **ONLY ONE**. This is the improvement you will work on tomorrow to make a detailed plan.

Of all these opportunities, which improvement seems most important to you right now? Which one would give you the most energy and desire to start?

Write down your decision here. This will be your Key Improvement. My Key Improvement to work on tomorrow is:

- Standardize recipe
- Look for innovative recipes
- Make innovative shapes and presentations

Analysis of the selected key improvements shows that participants focused on concrete and practical actions. Their decisions can be grouped into several categories:

- Innovation in the product and the value proposition. Several participants chose to improve or differentiate their offer. For example, an entrepreneur from the juice group chose "knowing how to preserve the pulp of each season" and "improving juices for diabetics" as an improvement, thus seeking to serve a niche market and better manage its resources. In the bakery and pastry group, another participant decided to "standardize recipes, look for innovative recipes, and make innovative shapes and presentations."
- Improvement of internal processes and capabilities. Other decisions focused on strengthening one's own skills and work efficiency. One participant, for example, defined her key improvement as "starting to make dough more often to... improve what I do," identifying the practice as a way to perfect her technique and the quality of her product.
- Market development and marketing. The need to reach more customers was also a focus. The same participant who sought to improve her technique through practice, also did so with the aim of "promoting and getting customers". Another entrepreneur, faced with the challenge of "not having transportation," connected it with the opportunity to "organize my time" in order to "get more customers."

This activity was a fundamental methodological step in the workshop. By asking participants to choose a single improvement, they were guided to prioritize and select a manageable starting point from a range of possibilities. This filtering process is crucial, as it transforms the overall problems and aspirations into a specific and concrete goal, thus laying a realistic basis for the elaboration of the action plan detailed in the next and final activity.

Activity 6. My improvement plan.

The final activity of the workshop consisted of the development of an improvement plan. In this step, participants translated the "key improvement" they had previously selected into a sequence of concrete and organized actions. Using a worksheet, each entrepreneur detailed the specific steps they were going to take, the resources they would need for each one, who would execute it (always being responsible for it themselves) and a timeline with start and end dates. The Figure 9 shows one of the plans developed.

Figure 9. Sample worksheet for activity 6. My improvement plan⁸.

INNOVAR Y ACTUALIZARNOS EN DISEÑOS Y ACCEDER A GRANDES COMERCIANTES PARA VENDER EN CANTIDAD Y QUE EN ALGUN MOMENTO EXPORTEN NUESTROS PRODUCTOS

Actividad 7. Hoja de Trabajo: Mi Plan de Mejora

Nombre de la Emprendedora: Arminda Rosales

1. El Reto que quiero superar (Mi Mejora Clave - Actividad 4):

2. La Ruta que he elegido para superarlo (Mi Estrategia Adoptada - Actividad 6):

3. Los Pasos que voy a dar (Mi Plan de Acción Detallado):

Paso	Acción	¿Qué necesito para ejecutarla?	¿Quién la ejecutará?	Inicio	Final
1	Realizar consultas al Internet para buscar nuevos diseños	Celular con el programa descargado	Yo con ayuda de mis hijos	20 julio	
2	Aprender a sacar nuevos diseños en tejido	Lana Hilo Brochel Aguja Maquina centimetrica + tijera + tarjetera	nosotras	20 julio	30 julio
3	Buscar proveedores accesibles	- Averiguar tiendas y direcciones - tiempo - dinero	nosotras	21 julio	26 julio
4	Publicar en redes las prendas.	- Celular - tiempo - dinero	Nosotras con ayuda de hijos	23 julio	23 julio
5	- Buscar clientes mayoristas para ofrecer producto	- Tiempo - Dinero - transporte	Contar con prendas de calidad Nosotras	23 julio	...
6					
7					

The resulting action plans are characterized by their practical approach and orientation to short-term results. The proposed actions can be classified into several areas:

- Training and product development. A significant part of the plans focused on acquiring new knowledge to improve the offer. Actions such as "learning simple recipes" through

⁸ Translation of the figure to English:

1. The Challenge I want to overcome (My Key Improvement - Activity 4): INNOVATE AND UPDATE OURSELVES IN DESIGNS AND ACCESS LARGE MERCHANTS TO SELL IN QUANTITY AND THAT AT SOME POINT THEY EXPORT OUR PRODUCTS

2. The Route I have chosen to overcome it (My Adopted Strategy - Activity 5): (Blank)

3. The Steps I will take (My Detailed Action Plan):

Step	Action	What do I need to execute it?	Who will execute it?	Start	End
1	Make queries on the mobile phone to look for new designs.	Mobile phone with the program downloaded	Me with the help of my daughters	July 20	July 20
2	Learn to create new designs in weaving.	Wool, needle, scissors, measuring tape, crochet hook	us [female]	July 20	July 30
3	Look for accessible suppliers.	Find out shops and addresses. Time Money	us [female]	July 21	July 26
4	Publish the garments on networks.	Mobile phone Time Money	us [female] with the help of my daughters	July 23	July 23
5	Look for wholesale customers to offer the product.	Time Money Transportation	Have quality sample garments	July 23	...

"virtual or face-to-face courses", "learning to bring out new designs in fabric" or "looking for innovative recipes" were proposed.

- Production and equipment. Concrete steps were detailed for the development of the products and the acquisition of the necessary tools. For example, tasks such as "buy cattle for fattening", "buy alfalfa cutting machine" or the need to "have a refrigerator" for better conservation of inputs were included.
- Commercialization and marketing. The participants defined strategies to reach new customers and promote their products. The plans included actions such as "looking for wholesale customers," "posting and offering product on social media," "opening a Facebook page," and "improving product presentation" with the use of hashtags.
- Business management. Actions related to the management of the enterprise were also identified, such as the need to "calculate costs and price" to ensure the profitability of the products.

When analysing the improvement plans, it is observed that they are, for the most part, viable and realistic. Their viability lies in the fact that the proposed actions are concrete, small-scale and short-term oriented. Tasks such as "learning simple recipes", "calculating costs" or "posting on social networks" are steps achievable with the resources that the participants themselves identified, such as a mobile phone or internet access. The work does not constitute an in-depth and exhaustive business analysis, but rather the successful application of a guided methodology that allowed them to translate a desired improvement into a sequence of logical steps. An important deduction is the immediacy of the plans. Deadlines, often set for the same week or month as the workshop, reflect a clear commitment to action. Likewise, the plans reveal a reliance on accessible technology as a key lever for learning (virtual courses) and marketing (social media), underscoring the importance of strengthening their digital skills for the growth of their ventures.

3.2 Analysis by productive sector

In addition to the analysis of the activities carried out, it is interesting to observe how the different groups of entrepreneurs applied the methodology according to the particularities of their sector. While the process was the same for all, the challenges, aspirations and, consequently, the resulting action plans, varied significantly between the groups of weaving, breakfast, livestock, bakery and baking, and juices. This analysis by productive sector offers a complementary vision that illustrates the flexibility of the approach and the richness of the solutions generated.

Weaving group (artisan)

This group focused its plans on innovating and updating its designs and accessing large merchants to sell in quantity, as well as on the possibility that, in the future, they could export products through those same merchants.

Indeed, the artisans showed a great desire to transcend the local market. Their action plan focused on exploring modern designs through Pinterest, actively searching for wholesale customers and merchants in Cochabamba, and market research using ChatGPT, Instagram, and TikTok. They were very open to creating innovative designs, garments and other types of

products, always controlling costs to ensure profitability. They also identified the need to find more affordable suppliers for their materials and the potential to post their garments on social media to expand their reach. They were very motivated by the idea that their creations could reach a wider audience.

The worksheets of this group reflect this strategic vision very clearly. The focus of its improvement plan was explicitly "to innovate and update ourselves in designs and access large merchants." This goal was directly connected to their dreams of "wholesale garment delivery" and "exporting to other countries." To achieve this, its action plan detailed steps such as "learning to bring out new designs", "looking for wholesale customers" and "looking for accessible suppliers", thus responding to the challenge identified that "the price of wool has gone up". Likewise, the intention to expand their reach was materialized in the action of "publishing and offering product" on social networks, for which they would need a "mobile phone with the program downloaded".

Breakfast Group

The breakfast group prioritized innovation in low-cost breakfasts and improving sales techniques to achieve a fair price. The main challenge for this group was their limited working capital, which led them to focus on innovation at low cost. Its plan includes the review of suppliers to optimize expenses and the exploration of new recipes to diversify its offer. A crucial point was the recognition of the need to improve their sales techniques to achieve fair prices and, in particular, the importance of interacting more with the customer to understand their tastes, orienting their offer to greater consumer satisfaction.

This approach is clearly reflected in the worksheets. Faced with the challenge that "all prices have gone up," one of the participants proposed in her improvement plan very specific actions such as making a "corn api in shell," described as "different from the typical," "more nutritious" and "economical." This idea is a perfect example of innovation at low cost, as it seeks to create new value from the same ingredients. Likewise, the need to "improve sales techniques" is connected to his dream that "my customers value my work and my seasoning", looking for a "fair price" through an offer that better responds to what the customer is looking for, such as a "healthy" and "warm different" product.

Livestock group

This group focuses on reducing feed costs, exploring the sale of manure and the use of fruit peels from other colleagues. Livestock participants clearly identified the opportunity to optimize their feed costs without compromising livestock quality. In addition, their action plan considers the possibility of selling manure as a valuable by-product and, very ingeniously, the use of fruit peels discarded by the juice group, which fosters an interesting synergy and collaboration within the community. A key aspect that was proposed was the organization to share transportation with others, seeking to reduce costs and thus increase their profit margin. He also proposed to look for cattle at a better price for fattening.

The worksheets of these entrepreneurs perfectly illustrate the prioritization of cost optimization. His main challenge identified was that "the fattening cattle went up, everything that the bulls consume went up", a problem that directly affects the viability of his dream of having "a modern fattening cattle stable with about 30 heads". Consequently, its improvement plan was oriented towards very specific actions to mitigate these costs, such as "buying cattle at a better price for

fattening", "buying feed for fattening" and "buying alfalfa cutting machine", which would allow it to process its own forage.

Figure 10. Working group carrying out one of the activities

Bakery and confectionery group

The bakery and confectionery group focused on innovation in recipes and packaging, as well as improving marketing. This group showed great receptivity to the workshops, focusing on the creativity and differentiation of their products. Its work plan is oriented towards the creation of recipes and ways of showing the different product, as well as the development of products that stand out in the market. A fundamental point is that they seek to understand their costs well. The organization for sales and marketing was a key point for them, looking for strategies that would allow them to reach more customers and optimize their sales.

The great receptivity of this group was reflected in their worksheets. The key improvement selected by one of the participants was "standardize recipes, look for innovative recipes, and make innovative shapes and presentations." The need for better marketing took the form of plans that included "learning how to make a visual menu," "opening a Facebook page," and "selling to order." For its part, the importance of understanding costs materialized in the specific action of "calculating costs and price", a direct response to the challenge that "things are very expensive" and the difficulty of selling by prices.

Juice group (first group)

The entrepreneurs working in the field of juices formed two distinct groups. The first focused on improving the mixtures of its juices and on the management of the fruit. Their plan included the search for new flavour mixtures and the strategy of storing seasonal fruit to have it at other times of the year, which would allow them to maintain the supply and control prices. They also set out to improve their sales techniques and the way they display their products, understanding that presentation is key to attracting customers.

This focus on product improvement and input management is seen in their worksheets. One of the participants identified as a key challenge "not selling our juices" and the need to "know how

to preserve the pulp of each season" to have product available. In her improvement plan, another entrepreneur in the group specified this strategy in actions such as "innovation of mixtures" and "having fruit all year round to save costs." The importance of presentation was also embodied in their plan, which included the creation of "labels" with "name and flavor," a direct action to improve the way they display their products and attract more customers.

Juice group (second group)

This second group of women entrepreneurs in the field of juices showed a great interest in innovation and in the creation of added value for their products. Their plan included creating unique concepts behind their juices, developing innovative blends and presentations, and researching the properties of fruits to communicate the benefits to their customers. They used ChatGPT as a key tool for this research, looking for each juice to have a defined story and purpose, which would add great value to their offering.

While the worksheets do not capture the direct use of tools such as ChatGPT, they do show the germ of this search for added value. The key improvement selected by one of the participants of "improve juicing for diabetics" is a clear example of creating a product with a defined purpose and aimed at a specific niche. Likewise, the dream of having "my own store and brand" reflects a mentality oriented towards innovation and the construction of a unique identity for its products, beyond the simple sale of a soft drink.

4. Analysis and conclusions

The project was a success in encouraging entrepreneurial self-discovery and the adoption of digital tools among the participants. Their interest and motivation were evident. It is worth noting the sacrifice that it meant for them to give up their activities and travel to participate in the sessions. The activity allowed them to lay the foundations for innovation in their ventures, by developing concrete work plans that trace the path for future actions, after defining several improvements and choosing a specific focus.

The effectiveness of the methodology applied lies, to a large extent, in its ability to guide the analysis through a structured itinerary. The process, which took them from the description of their operational reality to the formulation of an action plan, allowed the participants to move logically from diagnosis to solution. This approach was instrumental in transforming a general awareness of issues, such as rising costs, into a specific and achievable commitment to action. In this way, the action not only offered content, but also provided the entrepreneurs with a potentially replicable method for the future.

Beyond individual improvement plans, the group work revealed the existence of cross-cutting challenges that affect several entrepreneurs, such as the optimization of transportation or the purchase of inputs. Potential synergies emerged during the discussions, such as a proposal by a livestock participant to use discards from the juice group. Although the final plans are individual in nature, this identification of shared problems and solutions lays the groundwork for future partnership initiatives, which could amplify the impact of these improvements on a community scale.

It should be noted that the favourable outcome of the sessions held is clearly related to the methodology of co-creation and integration of knowledge used. Any approach that was based on

methods known to or devised by external technicians would have given rise to approaches that were alien to the reality of the participants and to themselves. The sessions gave the participants the opportunity to evaluate and discuss the situation and possibilities of their ventures, as well as to share their approaches among themselves and with the technicians, which gave rise to reflections and purposes that would not have otherwise occurred. All the analysis, however, was produced based on his own vision and his own views.

To ensure the success of these initiatives, it will be critical to provide continuous follow-up, helping to resolve issues that may arise and providing the necessary redirection to ensure that women can effectively execute everything they have set out to do. This support is key to transforming their plans into sustainable realities.